

**Samuel Adegboyega University,
Ogwa, Edo State**

PANDEMIC IN THE 21ST CENTURY: MULTIDIMENSIONAL APPROACHES

**Conference Proceedings for 2nd College of Management and
Social Sciences 2021 Conference held on 21st April 2021**

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RATIONALISING HUMAN RESOURCES IN NIGERIAN PUBLIC AND PRIVATE SCHOOLS IN THE COVID-19 ERA: CHALLENGES, TREND AND STRATEGY

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Abstracts

The study focused on rationalising human resources in Nigerian public and private schools in the era of Covid-19. The objective of the study is to examine whether the Elliott Wave theory can specifically determine the current and future wave pattern or trend of the covid-19 infection case timeline in Nigeria and how the education sector should strategise toward adjusting its human resources to fit into the new norm with exactitude. Trend analysis method was utilised in extrapolating data from Nigerian Centre for Disease Control (NCDC)/Statista and juxtaposing data derived from Focus Group Study conducted at selected public and private secondary schools in Delta, Anambra, Imo and Enugu states, to identify their immediate human resources response strategy. It was argued that the complexities and confusion of Human Resources Management (HRM) strategy response to the covid19 pandemic arose from the inability for HRM managers to predict the timeline of the covid19 virus behaviour spread pattern (accounting for the virus containment, control and exhaustion) and are most actively utilising intuitive reacting response and adaptations strategies; instead of applying the Elliot wave theory to predict future wave pattern and deploy an appropriate human resources strategy that fit into the expected trend with approximate exactitude. It was recommended that HRM strategy should descale major events, activities and spending reduction programmes pending the final exhaustion of the covid19 in 2023.

Keywords: Covid-19, Elliott Wave, Human Resources Strategy, Trend Timeline

Introduction

With the big jump from bat to human transmission in Wuhan-China and then from human to human transmission across the globe, the novel coronavirus (SARS-CoV-2) tagged Covid19 cause disease in its host, exhibiting human systemic disorder (initiating fever, cough, fatigue, sputum production, headache, haemoptysis, acute cardiac injury, hypoxemia, dyspoea, lymphopenia, diarrhea) and respiratory disorder (triggering Rhinoohoea, sneezing, sore throat, pneumonia, grand-glass opacities, RNAaemia, acute respiratory distress syndrome) (Rothana & Byrareddy 2020).

Spreading from Wuhan-China in December 2019 to across the global as at 4:44pm on March 25th 2021, the covid19 confirmed cases reported were 125,160,255 and 2,748,737 deaths. Nigeria

index case was imported from Milan-Italy to Ogun State on February 27th 2020 and by 25th of March 2021; confirmed cases reported were 162,275 and 2036 deaths (www.worldometer.info, Amzata, Aminub, Kolob, Akinyeleb, Ogundairob & Danjibob, 2020).

The World Health Organisation (WHO) identified Nigeria as a high-risk country with potential to spread the COVID-19 occasioned by its large trade link with China. Nigeria's population of over 206 million people, a health sector with low investment and poor facilities including low caregiver to patient ratio put the country as a potential threat for a super spread for the virus (Amzata *et al* 2020). The Presidential Task Force on Covid19 (PTF-Covid-19) in collaboration with the Nigerian Centre for Disease Control (NCDC) have instituted training for health workers and provided protocol for the fight against the covid19 pandemic in Nigeria. This includes providing health and other regulatory guidelines; such as restriction of movement, lockdown in epic states and nationwide travel cessation, closure of organisations, schools and worship centers at various scheduled intervals in 2020 and beyond (Aminub, Kolob, Akinyeleb, Ogundairob & Danjibob, 2020). Since the virus is spreading through close contact and the possibility of an infected person (not necessarily symptomatic) depositing respiratory droplets either on surface areas or in the air (shared environment), the covid19 has altered the work environment, cities, countries and continents (Caligiuri, Cieri, Minbaeva, Verbeke & Zimmermann, 2020), forcing organisation to face grand challenges more turbulent than climate change, severe economic downturns, and political instability (Carnevalea & Hatakb, 2020) and escalating a people-based crisis causing insecurity, disempowerment and vulnerability for the individuals and organisations. With this obvious challenge, the Human Resources Management (HRM) functions and specialists are at the forefront of the crisis surrounding both the individual and organisation in the pandemic era (Mwita, 2020).

Predictive technical indicator analysis assume that human emotions are not static or linear but occurs in wave arrangement and trend; researchers using the Elliott wave theory have been able to predict the future of price behaviour in stock, forex, index and future markets with high margin of exactitude. Can same theory be applied to determine the wave pattern of the covid19 infection rate to enable Human Resources manager provide adequate innovative strategy that fit into the trend (and provide advantage for organisation) without exacerbating panic outcome for organisation and employees?

Statement of the Problem

The Covid-19 independently altered the work space and condition, as human resources managers reacted with impulsive speed without specific strategic position in sight to deal with the pandemic. It was at best applying a coping mechanism to new challenge without end. What informed the spontaneity of the Human Resources Manager (HRM) response is the lack of opportunity to access the Covid-19 (like all natural phenomena) trend and pattern to determine the life span of the virus or exhaustion/collapse and consequently design an appropriate HRM strategy to deal with employees needs and organisational goal within the same time frame. The study is indicative of the compulsory closure of all schools in Nigeria by an order of the federal government under the advice of the PTF before or on march 28th 2020 (a month and day after the index case was reported); the education sector was considered a high risk sector owing to its large population and close contact environment amidst a growing rate of covid19 in Nigeria. The public-private secondary schools in Delta, Anambra, Imo and Enugu State is the focus of the study to investigate HRM strategy deployed in Nigeria during the first (minor) wave of the Covid-19 pandemic.

Research Objective

The research objective is to examine whether the Elliott wave theory can specifically determine the current and future wave pattern or trend of the Covid-19 infection case timeline in Nigeria and readjust the HRM strategy to fit into the environment of the new norm with certainty of prior knowledge and benefits to the employees and organisation without disturbing the balance of academic calendar or scheduled activities in public and private secondary schools in Nigeria.

Research Question

How and what HRM strategy was deployed by the education sector (that was heavily impacted by the Covid-19 in Nigeria) in public and private secondary schools' operations in Delta, Anambra, Imo and Enugu States.

Literature Review

Efficient organisations are essentially bureaucratic since they operate a purposive defined hierarchical structure that is linked to authority and responsibilities of officials according to superior and subordinate relationship gradation from which official decision and communication emanate from. These organisations are habitual in the form and method of operation contained in their rules, regulations and procedures that define a sense of organisational stability and predictability. Organisations that operate in this setting have crafted their internal and external environments and can account for and control their operational variables with certainty in a simple and routine fashion (Edigin, 2018; Podger, 2015; Sharma, Sadana & Kaur, 2013; Tonwe, 2008; StillmanII, 2005).

It is this stability and predictability in organisations' operations that the covid19 have altered. Organisations' external environments are now mortified with changing patterns of disruptions that wrecks the internal regularity and predictability of operations which organisations are accustomed to. Organisation leadership is unable to secure accurate and complete information that allow its structure to make appropriate strategic decisions and communication of its objectives to its human resources to pursue its goals. Organisations environment are now complex, multifarious and ambiguous (Madinda, 2014; Grote, 2009), following a disruptive impact of Covid-19 on the economic, political and socio-cultural systems surrounding and enclosing the organisation and all of its operations (Caligiuri, Cieri, Minbaeva, Verbeke & Zimmermann, 2020; Carnevalea & Hatakab, 2020; Mwita, 2020). Since the Covid-19 is a people-based pandemic and people are the most vital resources of organisation, the Human Resources Management department is now confronted with the challenge of developing appropriate strategic response to protect and maintain its human resources while also exploring means to continue with organisation's operation.

Less or little is known of the novel Covid-19, about its pattern of spread and life span in relation to the timeframe of its potency and exhaustion. If HRM can acquire this information through a focus on infection rate data of the Covid-19, it can codify its response from the position of strength than weakness or panic mode being currently displayed. HRM literature on response strategy to the Covid-19 has been captured in panic mode and fear since the information they are contained with are ambiguous and confusing. This places organisation, its resources and survival as vulnerable target that are not in control of their environment.

In a study conducted by Dogra, Koay, Wang, Vahidy, Ferrari, Pasqualini, Arap, Sostman & Cristini (2021), the Elliot wave principle was used to study the Covid-19 daily pandemic cases in America, India, Brazil and European Union Area. The findings showed the viability of the instrument for predictive purpose to aid policy makers in the health sector. The Elliot wave theory can effectively

predict natural phenomenon (that interacts with human emotion) in a definite trend and timeline accounting for its momentum, resistance and support levels as well as exhaustion. The Covid-19 assuming it is a natural phenomenon dealing with human emotional response, the Elliott wave can be deployed as a technical tool is equipping HRM to foster an appropriate human strategy to control the Covid-19 environment with exactitude and removing the confusion and complexities associated with its timeline from support to resistance along the path of the momentum and wave pattern. The Elliott wave theory is a technical analysis tool developed by Ralph Nelson Elliott to observe human emotion that is associated with price movement in the financial market. What is instructive in the Elliott wave theory is its basic assumption that implies universal applications in all human interactions.

Frost & Prechter (2006) and Rana (2016) noted that human behaviour depicted in emotions can be determine and predicted following how they occur overtime in historical pattern. Human emotion drive price in a wave clearly identified in the formation of a trend. This trend or pattern is fractural and can be mathematical calculated with high probability of occurring in real and future time. Price as well as any human emotional interaction does not move in linear or straight line; they naturally oscillate or move in wave pattern. The wave movement is repeated in up and down movements. The Elliott wave is an impulsive signal consisting of five sub-wave that net movement in the same direction (either upward or downward) till a correction initiate an obstruction to the trend. The typical wave cycle consists of eight waves with five waves to progress (motive) and three waves to regress (correction). There are major and minor wave in a pattern. Major waves have at least five waves in a trend while minor wave may serve as correction with three waves. Wave prediction is submerged in the trend structures. The structures are upward trend- bullish (highly predictable), downward trend-bearish (highly predictable) and range or sideways trend (unpredictable). The range trend is failing or point of indecision trend that lacks precision. The Elliott wave is highly predictable by ascertaining a prior trend structure (of either upward or downward trend) and unpredictable in a range structural trend.

Support in a trend is at a bottom point, which identified emotion or price that is predicted to raise upward and resistance is at the highest point which identified emotion or price predicted to move against the trend or reverse downward. The support and resistance of a trend essentially repeat overtime by forming a pattern that is consistent for an observer to make informed decision and predication. The Elliott wave can be supported with moving average or other indicators to make more informed decision and forecast of price movement reflecting of human emotion interaction. A wave function is either actionary (progressive) or reaction (correction). The direction of a wave depends on the degree to which a new wave further advances the cause of an existing larger wave or interrupt it with correction that is reactionary. Reactionary waves are countertrend wave that redirect the progression of a prior trend in the direction opposite to large wave formation. A motive larger wave may get extension (further progression) beyond the five sub-wave and ignore a correction. Motive waves are straightforward and can be easily recognise. Any five wave trend is a motive wave but a motive exhibit retraces in wave 2 and 4 (wave 2 retraces less than 100% of wave 1 and wave 4 retraces less than 100% of wave 3. Wave 1, 3 and 5 of a motive waves are actionary with wave 3 as the longest wave. Since corrective waves move against the trend of a motive trade, it generate this opposition through a struggling process from a point of resistance to the larger degree of the prior progression. The job of resistance is to enable the effect of a correction to actualise toward a downward trend. Correction waves are shorter with three waves (not fives).

Figure 1: Pattern Analysis depicting motive and corrective waves
 Frost & Prechter (2006), *The Elliott wave principle: Key to market behaviour*. Georgia, New Classics Library. www.elliottwave.com

Motive trend is labelled 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, but with retrace at 2 and 4), while correction is labelled ABC (with wave B serving as corrective wave). Waves are expressed in degree, with smaller degree or size serving as building block of the larger wave.

Methods

Trend analysis was used to analyse Covid-19 reported cases of infection rate in Nigeria and a Focus Group Study in Delta, Anambra, Imo and Enugu States. Trend analysis method was utilised in extrapolating data from Nigerian Centre for Disease Control (NCDC)/Statista. The data contained daily Covid-19 reported cases of infection rate in Nigeria. The monthly total infection rate is presented in figure 2 to show the trend of the infection and the wave pattern that occur between February 2020 and March 2021. Focus group study was also used to identify the response strategy adopted by public and private schools in Delta, Anambra, Imo and Enugu States. Ho (2006), Hargittai, Neuman & Curry (2012), Stewart, Shamdasani & Rook (2006) and Krueger (2002) note that focus group study or interview is concerned with the application of group discussion to discover

perception about their experiences or opinion about a subject of inquiry. The FGD range is between 6 to 10 participants to express their reactions to questions moderated by a researcher. Being a fact base research, the focus is on the judgement of the participant in qualitative expression.

The primary question in the focus group study was, what is the instruction offered by your principal/school management during the period of Covid-19 infection lockdown and during resumption (From March 2020 to March, 2021). The focus group study in Delta state focused on public secondary schools with 6 teachers drawn to participate in the focus group study. Two studies were conducted at Effurun and Udu with 6 teachers each participating in the focus group study. Separate Focus Group Study for Anambra, Imo and Enugu were conducted in Ekwulobia, Umudi and Ibagwa Nike respectively with 6 teachers participating at each location. The focus group studies were conducted across the 5 locations in the four states in the month of February and March 2021.

Data Presentation

Table 1: Covid-19 Timeline Daily Cases in Nigeria from February 2020 to March 2021

DAYS	Feb-20	20-Mar	20-Apr	20-May	20-Jun	20-Jul	20-Aug	20-Sep	20-Oct	20-Nov	20-Dec	21-Jan	21-Feb	21-Mar
1	0	0	39	238	416	790	386	239	153	111	281	980	676	360
2	0	0	10	218	241	626	304	261	126	72	122	576	1634	479
3	0	0	26	170	348	454	288	124	160	137	343	917	1138	464
4	0	0	4	244	350	603	304	156	58	155	324	1271	1340	711
5	0	0	18	148	328	544	457	162	120	180	310	1354	1624	371
6	0	0	6	195	389	573	354	100	118	223	318	1664	1588	195
7	0	0	16	381	260	503	443	155	155	59	390	1565	506	279
8	0	0	22	386	315	460	453	296	103	300	550	1544	643	400
9	0	1	12	239	663	499	457	176	151	94	474	1585	1056	346
10	0	0	17	248	409	575	290	179	111	152	675	1024	1131	394
11	0	0	13	242	681	664	423	188	163	180	796	1244	938	287
12	0	0	5	146	627	571	453	160	164	212	617	1270	1005	399
13	0	0	20	184	501	595	373	79	225	156	418	1398	1143	205
14	0	0	30	191	403	463	329	132	179	112	199	1479	520	120
15	0	0	34	288	573	643	325	90	148	152	758	1867	744	238
16	0	0	35	171	490	595	298	126	212	89	930	1958	1368	179
17	0	1	51	338	587	600	417	133	113	175	1145	1444	1073	187
18	0	5	49	216	745	653	410	221	133	120	806	1617	877	148
19	0	0	85	226	667	556	593	189	118	116	920	1301	662	130
20	0	4	38	276	661	562	476	97	72	209	501	1386	645	112
21	0	10	0	339	436	576	340	195	37	102	356	1964	521	86
22	0	8	208	245	675	543	601	176	138	192	999	1483	542	131
23	0	10	108	265	452	604	322	111	77	56	1133	2464	571	214
24	0	4	114	313	649	591	321	125	48	168	1041	964	655	96

25	0	7	87	229	594	438	252	231	62	198	784	1430	634	97
26	0	14	91	276	684	555	221	136	119	169	829	1303	600	113
27	0	5	64	389	779	648	296	126	113	246	838	1861	341	101
28	1	19	195	182	490	624	160	136	147	110	397	864	240	104
29	0	22	196	387	566	404	250	187	150	82	749	1650		
30		20	204	553	561	481	138	201	150	145	1016	1883		
31		4		307		462	143		162		1031	685		
TOTAL	1	134	1797	8230	15540	17455	10877	4887	3985	4472	20050	43995	24415	6946

Source: Simona Varrella @ www.statista.com and Nigeria Centre for Disease Control (NCDC)
 Fig. 2 Covid-19 trend rate per month

The daily and monthly entries of the Covid-19 are tabulated in table1 and the summary of the monthly infection rate is captured in fig. 2. It is the monthly total cases captured that is been utilised to show the trend of the infection rate of Covid-19 in Nigeria. The trend will enable human resources managers and other policy makers to identify trends and chose appropriate strategy to deal with the immediate situation and plan for the future in like manner.

Data Analysis

Using the summary of the Covid-19 infection rata data captured in the trend as exposed in fig. 2. It was clear in the histogram presented that the movement of the infection as recorded did not occur in a straight line. It rather, explicitly appeared in a wave showing rise and fall in momentum of recorded cases. The index case in February 2020 was the only case recorded for the month of February 2020, this identified the beginning of the wave 1, Wave 1 length stated with 1 case in February 2020 and peaked at July 2020 with 17455 cases recorded. Eliot wave identified that wave rises from low to

high from point 1 to 2. Wave 1 is a motive trend with impulse or actionary trend. Wave 2 begin with the decline from the end of wave 1 at a point know as resistance, where the infection rate began to decline through retraction or correction to a slope end. Wave 2 therefore began from July 2020 with a high record of 17455 recorded case to October 2020 to the end of a low/slope of 3895. Government initiated a lockdown in the last week of March and closure of schools within the same timeframe and reopen in October 2020. This is indicative that the Federal Government may be aware of the Elliot wave and responded to the trend in reopening the economy and schools in October 2020.

Wave 3 according to Elliot wave principle is a progression of the trend, an actionary or impulsive wave and is the longest among the three impulsive wave (of 1, 3 and 5). Wave 3 initiated an acceleration on a high motive with impulsive sequence indicating a rise from October 2020 with 3985 to January 2021 with a recorded case of 43955. The magnitude of the rise in wave 1 and 3, showed that the length of wave 3 is larger than wave1 as Elliott wave have predicted. Wave 4 like wave 2 is a retraction or correction caused by resistance. Wave 4 declined started in January 2021 with a recorded case of 43955 to March 2021, with a low recorded case of 6946 as at 29th of March 2021. Been that three days of 29-31 of March 2021 figures have not been recorded as at the time of this analysis, but the addition would not add any significant change to what is presented here.

According to Elliot theory, there are 5 waves in every motive trend of a progression. At this point, it is expected that the 5th wave will commerce at the end of March 2021 and progressed upward with recorded case lesser than wave three. The termination of the wave will end the exhaustion of a complete trend by identifying an upward general pattern in the movement of the virus. This according to Elliot wave is the initial completion of a minor wave in a major or large wave, which signifies the end of wave 1 in a major wave (at the completion of the subwave5). See figure 3 for diagramme.

Fig.3 showing major wave and minor formation

Source: Dogra, Koay, Wang, Vahidy, Ferrari, Pasqualini, Arap, Sostman and Cristini (2021). Do Pandemics Obey the Elliott Wave Principle of Financial Markets? @ medRxiv preprint doi: <https://doi.org/10.1101/2021.01.21.21250273>

Discussion

Focus Group Study for Delta state conducted at Effurun and Udu signified that all instructions concerning the managing of public secondary schools and response by teachers is coordinated by the Post Primary Education Board (PPMB) with headquarter at Asaba, the Delta State capital and the various local government secretariat at the local government area for supervision of schools under their jurisdiction in the local government. During the lockdown, teachers were instructed to teach their subjects online. But the programme was ineffective since the basic infrastructure and services required to conduct the programme were not provided by government and parents of the students did not provide the phones and data for their children/ward participation in the programme. However, radio and television classes were conducted as supplement for the online teaching. After the lockdown, when school resumed in October 2020 to March 2021, Schools were advised to practice social distancing.

Since the public schools were large in number of students they have, the PPMB adopted class rotation programme where a particular school is divided into two sections. Junior Secondary School 1-3 attend school on Monday, Wednesday and Friday every week while Senior Secondary School attend school on Tuesday and Thursday and Fridays. Only JSS3 and SS3 attend schools on Friday since they are certificate preparatory classes. During the lockdown and school resumption, public secondary schools' teachers in Delta State were paid their full salary regularly and as at when due. All inter-house competitions were cancelled for the 2020/2021 academic year.

The focus group study conducted in Anambra, Imo and Enugu States focused on private secondary schools in Ekwulobia, Umudi and Ibagwa respectively. The study revealed that during the lockdown, private schools' teachers were engaged in online learning and during resumptions the schools were divided into morning and afternoon sections. Morning sections were for all classes with relatively larger students while afternoon sections were for smaller classes. The division were relative to the nature of the class and school size. Morning section duration was from 8am to 12pm while afternoon section was from 12:30pm to 4:30pm on every working days of the week. Extra classes were cancelled for the moment. Teachers at the private secondary schools were not paid during the lockdown but were awarded stipend while after school resumption, teachers' salaries were initially reduced in the first term because of declining patronage and by the second term, teachers' salary were regularised. Few schools in Enugu reduced the numbers of teachers and increased the responsibilities of the teachers retained.

Finding

The covid19 cases reported from February 2020 to March 2021 as seen in table 1 and figure 2 and 3, revealed that the Elliot wave theory is applicable to the covid19 trend. It showed that the covid19 cases in Nigeria are in upward trend movement and at the end of the 4th wave, waiting currently to initiate the 5th wave of the exhaustion of a minor wave to its completion. As expected, the forecast is that the 5th wave of the minor wave will show increase in infection rate but not up to that of the 3rd minor wave. This means the expected 5th minor wave will end the completion of the large wave 1 in two or three months' interval for the retraction of a large wave 2 to emerge in the next three or four months with expected decline to follow in infection cases below the large wave 1 in length and size.

Conclusion

With the foresight and prior knowledge of the forecast of the Elliot wave theory, it is now expected for an informed HRM to initiate a formidable plan of action to enlighten staff of the expected rise and

fall of the virus infection with a definite timeline. Within the period of expected timeline for a rise in reported cases, organisation should reduce or slow down activities that requires overcrowding. This can also be substituted with the use of technology using teleconferencing and visual programming to conduct public events. It is also instructive to note that the large wave timeframe will exhaust at wave 5 while the retraction will exhaust at wave 3 where the virus will naturally disappear to outlive its time frame. With Elliott wave theory, major wave 1 will exhaust around July 2021 with expected rises in reported cases, and start to decline in large wave 2 with sub waves in between, to terminate with decline in cases reported around October 2021, then large wave 3 will emerge with higher infection that is ever reported from between October 2021 and March 2022, this period will require massive lockdown in 2022 longer and worse than in 2020 (as we have notice in 2020, a pandemic induced recession will follow that is severe than that of 2020, since more infection will be recorded and lockdown to stop the spread will be longer).

The trend will retrace with a resistance in April 2022 to June in large wave 4 with reduction in cases larger than wave2 but again the large wave 5 will get support from slope falling from July to October 2022 and begin to witness a large three wave retract but with increase in wave 2 of the retrace and the next will experience complete exhaustion and termination of the virus in mid or toward the end of 2023. The researchers are mindful of the application of vaccines at the moment, the controversies heralding the vaccines, the non-guarantees of the effects of the vaccine on people and the unwillingness of people to receive the vaccines have no significance in reducing the exhaustion timeframe of the Covid19 pandemic. Thus, organisations should prepare for lockdown and recession in 2022 and boom in 2024. HRM strategists equipped with the Elliot wave theory have come to indicate the natural rise and fall as waves in all human interaction as the economic indicators of 2020 has demonstrated and Covid-19 has shown. Organisation and HRM should begin to develop rotational schedules around the utilisation of human resources and consider restricting huge spending before 2024.

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